

Nutrihealth study: Folate and vitamin B12 status among Slovenian adults and elderly

Maša Hribar,^{1,2} Hristo Hristov,¹ Matej Gregorič,³ Urška Blaznik,³ Katja Zaletel,⁴ Adrijana Oblak,⁴ Joško Osredkar,^{4,5} Anita Kušar,¹ Katja Žmitek,^{1,6} and Igor Pravst^{1,2,6,*}

¹Nutrition Institute, Tržaška cesta 40, SI-1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia

²Biotechnical Faculty, University of Ljubljana, Jamnikarjeva 101, SI-1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia

³National Institute of Public Health, Trubarjeva 2, SI-1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia

⁴University Medical Centre Ljubljana, Zaloška cesta 7, SI-1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia

⁵Faculty of pharmacy, University of Ljubljana, Aškerčeva cesta 7, SI-1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia

⁶VIST–Higher School of Applied Sciences, Gerbičeva cesta 51A, SI-1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia

Folate and vitamin B12 (cobalamin) deficiencies can cause a series of health issues, including anemia, clinically presenting as tiredness, fatigue, shortness of breath, and muscle weakness. They mainly occur due to gastric malabsorption primarily in the elderly, and insufficient dietary intakes. Good dietary sources of folate are leafy green vegetables, legumes, and some fruit, whereas vitamin B12 naturally occurs only in animal source foods, and its intake is therefore usually low in vegetarian and vegan diets. In Slovenia, epidemiological data on folate and vitamin B12 status were investigated for the first time within a Nutrihealth study—an extension to the national dietary survey SI.Menu (2017/18) (1). The study was conducted on a representative sample of 125 adults (18–64 years) and 155 elderly (65–74 years old) subjects. Serum folate and vitamin B12 were measured as biomarkers, together with homocystein. Internal threshold for low folate status was set at 6.7 nmol/L, and low vitamin B12 level was set at serum concentrations below 150 pmol/L. The prevalence of low vitamin B12 status was 4.8 % in adults and 11.6 % in the elderly, while the prevalence of low folate status was 18.4 % in adults and 18.1 % in the elderly population. The study results are showing that the elderly have more than one time higher prevalence of vitamin B12 deficiency than adults, whereas the prevalence of poor folate status is similar in both age groups. The higher prevalence of vitamin B12 deficiency in the elderly indicates a need for better vigilance in addressing deficiency in this population.

References:

- (1) Nutrihealth Study: Seasonal Variation in Vitamin D Status Among the Slovenian Adult and Elderly Population. *Nutrients* 2020, 12(6), 1838; <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu12061838>